

AN OVERVIEW OF MICROBIAL CONTAMINATION AND PUBLIC HEALTH

Babajanova Gulchekhra Bakhtiyorovna

Assistant at the Medical faculty of Alfraganus University

Email: gulchexra197129@gmail.com

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Abstract

Microbial contamination of food can occur at any point in the food supply chain, from production to consumption. Therefore, it is essential to follow proper hygiene and manufacturing practices throughout the entire process to prevent microbiological contamination, which can lead to significant morbidity and mortality among consumers. Recent research has focused on developing innovative technologies to improve food safety and quality without compromising its taste or nutritional value. Future studies should prioritize the creation of simple, cost-effective, and rapid tests for detecting and controlling microbial contamination, as well as the development of new food processing techniques.

Keywords: microbial contamination, food contamination, innovative technologies, public health, foodborne diseases, food hygiene, food safety, good hygienic practices, manufacturing practices.

Currently, there is growing interest in food hygiene, safety, and the incidence of foodborne diseases due to their close connection to public health. Microbiological contamination of food by pathogenic microorganisms, along with their persistence, replication, and toxin production, has become a significant concern for consumers, the food industry, and regulatory agencies worldwide. Contamination can occur at any stage of the food chain but can be prevented by adhering to good manufacturing practices, implementing Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) principles, ensuring raw material control, and maintaining the cold chain at both industry and retail levels. This contamination includes not only the growth of harmful microbes but also the production of toxic metabolites, such as mycotoxins, or the formation of biofilms.

Microbial contamination is also closely linked to food losses resulting from spoilage and waste. As the global human population continues to grow, so does the demand for food. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations estimates that one-third (1.3 billion tons per year) of food produced for human consumption is lost due to spoilage or waste. Poor waste management can pose public health risks and lead to environmental problems such as disease outbreaks and air pollution. Although foodborne disease transmission has received more attention due to its direct public health implications, food spoilage also leads to significant economic losses, negative publicity for the food industry, and reduced food supplies. Effective food management is increasingly recognized as a critical factor for sustainable development and achieving global sustainability goals (SDGs 12 and 13). Reducing food waste offers both economic and environmental benefits, contributing to more sustainable food systems.

1. Foodborne Diseases

Microbial foodborne diseases (FBD) are a major public health concern due to the high risk of microbial contamination from various biological hazards. These diseases cause significant personal suffering, preventable deaths, and an avoidable economic burden. Each

year, at least two billion people worldwide are affected by FBD, making it one of the most pressing public health issues today..

Every stage of the food supply chain—from production to consumption—can pose a potential risk for FBD, whether through food production, processing, packaging, transportation, or handling. Consumers, as the final point in the food safety chain, are often referred to as the “final line of defense” against FBD. Common symptoms caused by foodborne pathogens include nausea, vomiting, abdominal discomfort, diarrhea, fever, and loss of appetite.

Preventing foodborne diseases requires implementing good manufacturing practices, rigorous control of raw materials, and maintaining the cold chain throughout the industry and retail sectors. Several studies have underscored the importance of food safety training and education for food handlers, as gaps in knowledge about microbial hazards, food storage temperatures, cross-contamination risks, and personal hygiene can contribute to FBD outbreaks. Strengthening education and training for food handlers can improve food handling practices, ensuring both food safety and quality for consumers, and reducing the incidence of foodborne diseases.

2. Food Preservation Techniques

To enhance the safety and extend the shelf life of food products, several traditional food preservation methods have been used to control microbial growth. These include techniques such as chilling, freezing, nutrient restriction, reducing water activity, acidification, pasteurization, sterilization, fermentation, and the use of chemical and biological antimicrobials. Among these, thermal treatments are the most widely applied methods for microbial inactivation in the food and beverage industries. However, these methods often negatively affect the sensory and nutritional properties of food, leading to reduced consumer acceptability. The current challenge is to improve food safety and quality without compromising nutritional, functional, and sensory attributes, driving the development of innovative technologies in the food industry.

In response, several non-thermal treatments have been developed that do not rely on raising food temperature to inactivate bacteria. These innovative techniques aim to improve food safety and shelf life. One such approach involves the use of free or encapsulated natural antimicrobial compounds, either alone or in combination with other technologies, to reduce microbial populations in food products. Recent studies have focused on the use of nisin-loaded nanoparticles as an effective antimicrobial agent in food formulations and packaging. These nano-carriers, which include nano-liposomes, nano-emulsions, solid lipid nanoparticles, and bio-polymeric nanoparticles, offer benefits such as sustained release, prevention of undesirable interactions, and high stability, all while preserving the sensory and nutritional qualities of food during storage.

Another emerging technology in the food industry is High Hydrostatic Pressure (HHP), a non-thermal method that inactivates a wide range of foodborne pathogens and harmful enzymes by applying pressures above 100 MPa through mechanically pressurized water. This process minimally impacts the overall quality, nutritional value, and flavor of the food. Pressures between 300 and 600 MPa have been shown to effectively prevent microbial growth, ensuring the quality and safety of food products.

A novel approach gaining popularity in the scientific community is antimicrobial photodynamic treatment (aPDT). This technique involves the use of visible or near-infrared light combined with a photosensitizer (PS) in the presence of molecular oxygen to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are responsible for microbial cell death. Since ROS can interact with various biomolecules and cell structures, the development of resistance to aPDT is a potential concern, and further studies are needed. Nevertheless, the use of non-toxic photosensitizers and harmless visible light makes aPDT a promising alternative for food applications, as it can inactivate a wide range of microorganisms, including bacteria (both vegetative cells and spores), yeasts, molds, protozoa, and viruses.

Research by Woo-Ju et al. has explored the non-thermal effects of microwave radiation, which can reduce pathogen presence and inactivate enzymes while preserving the nutritional properties of foods. Factors influencing the effectiveness of microwaves for microbial inactivation include power levels, electric field frequency, treatment duration, and the geometry and dielectric properties of the food. While research on this topic is still limited, further studies are necessary to optimize microwave technology for reducing microbial contamination in food.

Food irradiation has also garnered attention as a non-thermal technology, applying ionizing radiation in small doses to decontaminate food and extend its shelf life by damaging bacterial DNA. However, concerns over potential radioactivity generation in food make this technique controversial. Additionally, the low penetration power of irradiation limits its efficiency, especially on foods with irregular surfaces. Therefore, it has been suggested that combining irradiation with other technologies could provide a more effective solution for controlling microbial contamination in food.

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